

MUSICOLOGY

NIKOLAS KARLOVICH MEDTNER AND HIS SONATA-TRAGICA OP 39, NO 5.

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Abstract

Medtner is an unusual phenomenon in the history of Russian and world classical piano music. An artist with a distinctive personality, Medtner did not join any musical styles typical to the first half of the 20th century. A young contemporary of Scriabin and Rachmaninoff, he was a great pianist and composer like them, and his main compositional focus was on his own instrument, the piano.

The present paper attempts to show the facts of his life and career as a composer who developed the sonata genre in his own way.

Keywords: sonata, piano, instrument, composition, interpretation, conservatory, genre, concert.

Nikolas Karlovich Medtner was born in Moscow on January 5, 1880. His family has a rich artistic tradition. His mother, Aleksandra Karlovna Gedike - a sister of Feodor Gedike, the famous Russian composer and pianist; brother Emil was a philosophical writer and music critic; another brother, Alexander, was a violinist and conductor. In 1900, after graduating from the Moscow Conservatory as a pianist with a Minor Gold Medal from the class of Professor Safonov, Medtner soon attracted public attention as a young, talented pianist with solid technique and interesting, thoughtful interpretation.

Despite his early talent to compose music, he did not receive systematic compositional education. During his conservatory year, Medtner took classes on counterpoint and fugue with Taneyev only for one semester. His wife Anna Medtner later evidenced that "Nikolas loved to show his works to Sergey Ivanovich Taneyev and always been happy when received approval from him."¹ His primary source of compositional skill comes from his self-study samples of classical music literature.

Medtner, as a young composer and pianist, was enthusiastically received by the public. Along with concerts of Rachmaninoff and Scriabin, Medtner's concert evenings were essential events in the music life of Russia and abroad.

His first concert as a composer took place on March 26, 1903, in Moscow, where he performed music of Bach, Beethoven, Chopin, and several pieces from his cycle called "8 Sentimental Pictures" op 1.² (Acht Stimmungsbilder)

In the same year, the entire cycle was published by the Moscow music publishing house Jurgenson. The music was favorably received by Russian music critics, who noted the composer's early maturity and expression of his unique artistic personality.

The subsequent significant work that followed Op. 1 was the Sonata in F minor, on which Medtner worked in 1903-1904, guided by Taneyev's advice. This music has a pathetic emotional character, and compared with

his previous work, it differs with its "muscular" firm texture, main themes with different conciseness, and elasticity of rhythm. It was an impetus to his further development as a sonata composer.

Beginning with this first experience of the new form, the sonata genre plays an essential role in Medtner's works. He composed fourteen piano sonatas and three sonatas for violin and piano. Still, suppose we add his other works based on the principles of sonata form (concertos, quintets, and even some of the pieces of minor form). In that case, we can confidently say that no other contemporary of Medtner in Russia did not develop this form with tenacity and perseverance, as did Medtner. But, having learned the compositional achievements of the classical and romantic era's sonata form, Medtner develops his new ways. First of all, public attention should be drawn to the extreme diversity of his sonatas, differing from each other in the expressive nature of music and the structure of the cycle. Regardless of the size and number of pieces, Medtner strives for consistency from the beginning to the end with the single poetic idea, which in some cases indicates titles like Sonata-Reminiscenza, Sonata-Ballade, Sonata-Tragica or starts with a poetic epigraph.

Being a distinguished pianist, he fully and vividly showed himself in the field of piano music. Medtner has sixty-one published opuses, and almost two-thirds of them are written for the piano. A significant and often dominant role belongs to the piano in his other works (songs, violin sonatas, and the quintet). Before going abroad, when conditions of his life forced him to expand his performance activities, Medtner loved to perform his music and considered those performances to be a kind of report of his creative achievements in music. This was his talk and statement to the public.

Medtner did not like to perform in large concert halls in front of an extensive public. He preferred smaller chamber music halls. Attraction to intimacy was very characteristic of Medtner's artistic image. In a response to his brother Emil's letter, he wrote: If my music is "intimate," it is because the music is born from

¹ Leonid Sabaneev. *Modern Russian Composers* Freeport, NY: Books for Libraries Press 1967, 88

² Apetyan, Zarui Apetovna. N.K. Medtner: *Vospominaniya, Stati, materialy* Moskva: Vses.izd-vo Sovetski kompositor, 1981, 71

our intimate with the art mind. I consider that it will be my duty to remind people about that.³

One of Medtner's most famous piano works was a tale—a small work of lyrical and epic character. He wrote stories about the different experiences he had seen, heard, or read and about the events of his inner spiritual life. Featuring a wealth of imagination and diversity of nature, Medtner's Fairy tales vary in scope. We can find more detailed and complex form pieces along with simple, unpretentious miniatures. The first of these was composed in 1905.⁴

At the same time, Medtner worked on vocal music. In the summer of 1903, when he first began a serious interest in poetry and literature, he discovered Goethe, and this was the beginning of his understanding of the secret power of the poetic world. At that time, he wrote to his brother Emil that he had been getting excited about this art since he discovered Goethe. From 1904 to 1908, he wrote three song cycles of poems by Goethe. The composer wrote them in the original German text, which allowed him to retain all the features of the author's poetic language. The Goethe cycles showed the composer's highest achievements in the field of vocal music; they were appreciated by his contemporaries, and in 1912, he was awarded the Glinka Prize.

After creating a kind of "musical offering" to his highly valued German poet, Medtner, in the future, wrote mainly Russian poetry. In 1911-1914, he wrote several songs on poems by Tyutchev and Fet, but the composer's focus drew Pushkin's poetry. It can be said that the following years for Medtner were years of Pushkin. In 1913-1918 Medtner created three Pushkin cycles, one after another. These are Medtner's undoubted successes and contributions to Russian poetry, as well as the two vocal songs "The Muse" and "Arion."

Medtner's teaching activities were very successful. In 1909-1910 and 1915-1921, Medtner was a piano professor at the Moscow Conservatory. Among his students, we can find names of prominent Russian musicians such as A. Shatskess, N. Shtember, and B. Chaikin. Both Sofronitsky and Oborin are consulted with Medtner, too.⁵ His students and colleagues considered him as a master of polyphony. For Medtner, the goal of composition and performance was to merge contrapuntal style with musical harmony; a supreme example of this Medtner was Mozart.

Medtner had little interest in the outer and sensual side of sound paint. For him, the main logic of music was the expression of thought or feeling in a complete harmonic structure, which is an element strongly linked to and subordinated to a single concept. In his point of view, an excessive abundance of colors would only distract the listener's attention from developing fundamental ideas, weakening the strength and depth of experience.

Medtner's piano concertos are monumental pieces. The best of these is the First Concerto. This relatively small one-movement concerto has great inner wholeness and unity of conception. Medtner worked on this concerto for four years. In the summer of 1917, he wrote to his brother Emil, "The concert had started three years ago and still was not finished. However, the music is quite finished, but only the instrumentation does not go well. It is hard for me to write the instrumentation because I am essentially an improviser."⁶

One of the best of Medtner's and beloved by listeners and performers Sonatas is Sonata-Tragica, in C minor, op 39, No 5, written in 1918-1920. This is Medtner's only monothematic sonata in which the outcome of the music is already present at the beginning, unaffected by any development, a closed circle, an inescapable conclusion.

Although Medtner wrote a wild and brilliant coda in this work, this sonata reminds listeners of the progression of similar mood and musical experience which has in his "Night Wind" Sonata op 25, No.2. Like the famous Sonata-Reminiscenza op 38, this work is also a part of a collection of his pieces called *Forgotten Melodies*, a title which mixes the naivety and irony very typical of Medtner. Years before this work was written, another famous Russian composer, Anton Arensky, had composed a six-part piano piece called "Essays on Forgotten Rhythms." The Sonata-Tragica can be performed as an independent piece, but Medtner wished this piece to be conducted as a two-movement work. His own published directive, "Attaca la Sonata tragica," appears at the end of *Canzona matinata*; the piece precedes this work in this opus. The emotional intensity and turbulence of this Sonata are in very remarkable contrast with the delicacy of the Sonata-Reminiscenza, and the only shared feature of these two works is the single-movement form. Another work of Medtner that most closely relates to the Sonata-Tragica is his first Concerto, also written in C minor, which has a tragic theme similar to the five abrupt blows of fate. The secondary theme of the sonata has a different and quiet character in a primary key. However, if we connect this Sonata to the *Canzona Matinata*, the character's melancholy will still be heard. In the development, recitative-like statements in the bass line will evolve into a single sequence of fragments of the main theme and the theme from *Canzona Matinata*. This is the last time the theme of *Canzona Matinata* is being heard in this sonata. The recapitulation moves towards a tragic and emotional power incorporating cadenza. The coda is a furious conclusion in which Medtner characteristically brings the first blows of fate with which this sonata began.⁷

This Sonata was premiered by the composer in Moscow in November 1920 and received with great interest from the fellow musicians of Medtner. This was the last piano sonata he wrote in his homeland before he went to the West.

³ Paperno, Dmitri. Notes of Moscow Pianist, Portland, Ore: Amadeus Press, 1988, 62

⁴ Rimm, Robert. The composer pianists: Hamelin and The Eight Portland, Or: Amadeus Press, 2002, 134

⁵ Holt, Richard. Nikolas Medtner, 1879-1952; A Tribute to his art and personality, D.Dobson: London 1955, 53

⁶ Miller, Sydney. "Medtner's Piano Music: An Appreciative Study" *The Musical Times* Vol, 82 No 1184 (Oct., 1941) pp, 361-363.

⁷ Martyn, Barrie. *Nikolas Medtner: His life and music* Aldershot, hants. England: Scholar Press, 1995, 140

Over ten years, he passed before Medtner wrote another piano sonata. During this time, he settled in France and then England. Although he returned to Russia for a successful concert tour, hopes of ever seeing his homeland again were dashed a few years later when the performance of his music was discouraged in the Soviet Union.

In 1921, he left Russia. He had concert tours in France, Germany, England, Poland, the United States, and Canada. In 1927, he came to the USSR and toured the program of his works in Moscow, Leningrad, Kyiv, Kharkiv, and Odesa.⁸

Not only the development of music in the 20th century but the whole structure of the modern world forced Medtner to preserve the purity of his own dear and spiritual values and ideals because his musical ideas were different. He never had an interest in "modern" music. But it was impossible to isolate himself from what was happening in reality, and the echoes of current events found conscious or unconscious influences in his music. The Sonata Minacciosa (Tempest Sonata), composed in the early 1930s, was called by Medtner the most modern of his works because this music reflects the stormy atmosphere of the events of the time.⁹

The book "The Muse and Fashion" was published in Paris in 1935, and it was a major event in his life. In this book, he expressed his thoughts and opinions, which are the results of long and concentrated thoughts of Medtner throughout his adult life. He was sharply critical of the current state of music composition and called it "Upset of the Lyre."

Medtner considered that new changes in music composition art, like atonality and twelve-tone music, are much different than his own music's "meaning," he believed that "new trends in music" were the main reason for the musical crisis and confusion among people.

Since 1936, Medtner lived in England, where his music was accepted and recognized. While there, he continued to regard himself as a Russian musician and said that he would never essentially be an immigrant and would not be one.

He died in London on 13 November 1951.

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⁸ Sabaneev Leonid and S.W. Pring, "Nikolai Medtner," *The Musical Times* Vol.69 No 1021 (Mar., 1928) pp. 209-210 <http://www.jstor.org/stable/916075>. accessed October 10/10/2011 00: 16

⁹ Medtner, Nikolai. *The Muse and The Fashion*, trans. Alfred Swan. Haverford College: Haverford, 1951, 35